

The Implementation Of Retroactive Principles In Extradition Treaties Is Viewed From The Aspect Of Constitutional Law

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Abstract- The retroactive implementation of the principle in the extradition treaty between Indonesia and Singapore in 2022 aims to return corruptors who fled to Singapore. The retroactive application of this principle is retroactive to 18 years, meaning that corruptors who committed crimes before the treaty was ratified can be extradited and processed in accordance with applicable law. Judging from the aspect of constitutional law, the implementation of these principles and agreements must be adjusted to the laws and regulations in force in Indonesia, in other words, the Indonesian government must immediately make legislation derived from this agreement, so that in prosecuting corruptors there is a legal basis. In general, constitutional law has the authority, namely regarding matters related to the state, meaning that anything that is bound by the state can be said to be still within the scope of constitutional law discussion. Both in the form of constitutional structures, institutions in the state or the relationship of one organ with certain organs in the state, and discusses the relationship between state structures and citizens. In relation to constitutional law, it is known that there are two functions of Indonesian constitutional law, namely as a legal basis for the establishment of the Indonesian national legal system and also as a legal basis for the formation of organizational structures and work relations in the Republic of Indonesia.

Keywords- Retroactive base, Extradition Treaty, Constitutional Law.

I. INTRODUCTION

The signing of the extradition treaty between Indonesia and Singapore on January 25, 2022 in Bintan, Riau Islands caught the attention of several foreign media, making headlines related to the Indonesia-Singapore extradition treaty. The long road of ratification of this treaty is to follow up on the previous extradition treaty ratified in 1998, which in the 1998 extradition treaty did not provide for the extradition of corruptors, so with the ratification of the extradition treaty again in 2022, corruptors and other criminals who fled to Singapore have a narrower space. According to Law and Human Rights Minister Yasonna H Laoly said, "this extradition treaty has retroactive validity from the date of promulgation for the last 18 years". This follows the maximum expiry provisions as stipulated in Article 78 of the Criminal Code [1] Indonesia's main interest behind this Extradition Treaty is the arrest of corruptors who mostly fled to Singapore and the return of state assets corrupted by these corruptors, especially the corruptors in the BLBI (Bank Indonesia Liquidity Assistance) case in 1998, and several other corruption cases, which until now the perpetrators are still fleeing and are in Singapore such as Maria Pauline who has cost the state Rp 1.7 trillion, Agus Anwar, convicted of Bank Pelita's BLBI corruption case, fled to Singapore and is rumored to have changed his nationality, Kirana Kotama, convicted of the Hamalang project corruption case, fled to Singapore after being released on parole in 2015. He was re-arrested in Singapore in 2021 and extradited to Indonesia. However, the extradition process is still pending until now, Eddy Sindoro, a fugitive for corruption and fraud, reportedly fled to Singapore in 2009.[2]

The escape of corruptors abroad, especially to Singapore in addition to avoiding legal entanglement, also for money laundering / TPPU (money laundry). TPPU itself as a crime has a distinctive characteristic, namely that this crime is a double crime, not a single one. The form of money laundering activities is characterized by the form of money laundering as a follow-up crime, while the original crime is referred to as predicate offense / core crime or as unlawful activity, namely the original crime that produces money which is then carried out by the laundering process.[3] Coordinating Minister for Polhukam Mahfud MD revealed a number of money laundering modes that occur. He said the first mode was to take rupiah bills abroad to be exchanged into dollars and claimed as gambling proceeds. "This evil way of corruption is also money laundering. That money, haram money is lawful. For example, there is a county official on the other end, what is the transfer budget from the center... Rp 2 trillion, then the money was lowered, Rp 600 billion was lowered. He brought Rp 600 billion in cash abroad," Mahfud said during a national dialogue entitled 'National Strategy in the Field of Polhukam to Anticipate Global Political Dynamics' at the National Police Training Institute.[4]

"When the money is unloaded from the bank, it is not written for what and to what account, for what project, anyway this is for development. Brought gambling to Singapore, to Malaysia, to Las Vegas. The return of the money has become dollars," he continued. Mahfud said, when he arrived abroad, money launderers then went to gambling places to ask for a certificate. The money is then put into a personal account under the pretext of winning gambling results. "Actually, they were not gambling there, they exchanged money and then asked for a certificate that he came to the gambling house, later entered Indonesia. This is my money halal, why? I gamble and gambling in Singapore is okay. Log in to the bank personal account. After checking, I won the gambling. That's called money laundering. Illicit money is entered into accounts as if it were halal, laundered," he said. In addition to gambling, another mode of money laundering is to use the money to build a business. In fact, according to Mahfud, the business did not sell, but the income was not reasonable.[4]

The predicate and negative classification obtained by corruption crimes cause this crime to potentially be beyond the reach of conventional criminal law. Of course, to combat this criminal act, an extraordinary effort is needed (extraordinary action). These actions are for example actions that are sophisticated, innovative and full of breakthroughs.[5] Not only perfunctory actions such as just discourse or punishing corruptors selectively. Robert Kiltgard assessed, eradicating corruption will not succeed if only using a normative approach. There must be a progressive breakthrough that normative circles might consider strange.[6] In consideration of Law No. 20/2001 concerning the Eradication of Corruption which states that: "corruption that has occurred widely, not only harms state finances, but also is a violation of the social and economic rights of the community at large, so that corruption crimes need to be classified as crimes whose eradication must be carried out extraordinarily" [7]

Therefore, it is naïve to ignore religious teachings as a solution to sensitize corrupt actors while eradicating the root of corruption. In Islam corruption is strictly forbidden, as the hadith of the Holy Prophet (peace be upon him) narrated by Ibn Abbas (may Allah be pleased with him) said, "There will be no entry into heaven, a body that is fed with the haram. Word of Allah (swt) in the Quran surah Al-Baqarah verse 188

وَلَا تَأْكُلُوا أَمْوَالَكُم بَيْنَكُم بِالْبَاطِلِ وَتُدْلُوا بِهَا إِلَى الْحُكَّامِ لِتَأْكُلُوا فَرِيقًا مِّنْ أَمْوَالِ النَّاسِ بِالْإِثْمِ وَأَنْتُمْ تَعْلَمُونَ

Wa laa taakuluu amwaalakum bainakum bilbaatili wa tudluu bihaaa ilal hukkaami litaakuluu fariiqam min amwaalin naasi bil ismi wa antum ta'lamuun

"And let not one part of you eat the property of the other part of you in a foolish way, and (do not) you bring (the business) of the property to the judge, so that you can eat part of the property of another by sin, when you know"

Even though many efforts have been made by the government and religion, it has clearly forbidden, however, corruption in Indonesia continues to increase, both in terms of the quantity of cases that occur and the quality of corruption crimes committed by perpetrators tend to be more systematic, more widespread, and more damaging to every line of people's lives".[8] The large number of criminal offenders in Indonesia who fled to other countries, especially to Singapore to avoid criminal law bondage, resulted in obstacles for Indonesian law enforcement officials to enforce the law against the perpetrators of these crimes. Therefore, on January 25, 2022, Indonesia finally signed an extradition treaty with Singapore.[9] This extradition treaty allows both countries to extradite criminal offenders who although the type of crime is not directly mentioned in this treaty but has been regulated in the legal systems of both countries, the scope of the Indonesia-Singapore extradition treaty is that both countries agree to extradite any person found to be in the territory of the requested and wanted country by the requesting country to be prosecuted or tried or the execution of punishment for extraditable crimes.[10]

In addition, this extradition treaty will narrow the space for criminals in Indonesia to escape. The reason is, Indonesia already has agreements with regional partner countries including Malaysia, Thailand, the Philippines, Vietnam, Australia, the Republic of Korea, the People's Republic of China, and Hong Kong SAR. Yasonna believes that with this international agreement, corruptors and drug dealers can no longer hide in Singapore. This extradition treaty will create *deterrence* for criminals in Indonesia and Singapore.[11] In this extradition treaty, especially for corruptors, the principle of retroactivity is applied. In Black's Law Dictionary it says *Retroactive* is *extending in scope or effect to matters that have occurred in the past*. In Indonesia, the term that is close and often used is 'retroactive'. This *non-retroactive* principle is usually also associated with the principle in criminal law which reads *nullum delictum noela poena sine praevia sine lege poenali*. [12] (No act can be punished except on the strength of criminal rules in legislation that existed before the act was committed). In Indonesia, 2 (two) rules relating to the principle of *non-retroactive* or prohibition of retroactive enforcement of a law are in Article 28 i of the 1945 Constitution and Article 1 paragraph (1) of the Criminal Code.[13]

The application of this principle is actually not absolute, there are exceptions, such as those contained in Article 1 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Code and criminal acts categorized as *extra ordinary crimes*. Both rules are basically applications of the principles in criminal law, therefore it is not strange that many people argue that the *principle of non-retroactivity* only applies to material criminal law.[14] This is further strengthened if article 28 i of the 1945 Constitution above is interpreted with existing methods of legal interpretation, it can be seen that the article is intended only for criminals, especially material crimes.[15] In addition to the problem of limited criminal law

capabilities in tackling crime, our criminal law is also less adaptive in responding to developments that occur in society, both national and international communities.[16]

When related to the Indonesian Constitutional Law, the retroactive enactment of the principle in this extradition treaty is generally not applied because it can create legal uncertainty and harm the sense of justice. Retroactive means that a regulation or policy is applied backwards in time, which can cause uncertainty because people cannot with certainty anticipate the legal consequences that may arise from actions or decisions that have already been made. Therefore, this principle is avoided to maintain legal certainty and justice.[17] The retroactive principle and extradition treaties are related to the principle of state sovereignty. Retroactive relates to the way the law is applied backwards in time, while extradition treaties relate to interstate cooperation in the arrest and surrender of perpetrators of cross-border crimes.[18] The principle of state sovereignty emphasizes that each state has the right to exercise its own legal authority within its territory. In this case, retroactive principles and extradition treaties can be sensitive because retroactive enactment or handing over of a criminal to another state involves interference in a country's jurisdiction.[19]

The principle of retroactivity and extradition treaties must be carefully regulated in Indonesian constitutional law in order to maintain a balance between state sovereignty and human rights.[20] The retroactive principle, which involves retroactive enactment, and extradition treaties, which involve the transfer of offenders between states, are legal aspects that can affect a country's sovereignty and human rights.

Based on the above background, the author is interested in conducting in-depth and detailed research regarding: 1) How is the retroactive principle in the 2022 Indonesia-Singapore Extradition Treaty implemented in Indonesian constitutional law? 2) How aspects of Constitutional Law affect the retroactive implementation of the principle in extradition treaties between the two countries.

II. DISCUSSION

Retroactive Implementation of Extradition Treaty in Indonesian Constitutional Law

The retroactive implementation of the extradition treaty principle in Indonesian constitutional law is complex. In general, the retroactive principle implies the application of laws to events in the past. However, in the context of extradition, the application of the retroactive principle may involve several considerations that need to be considered. The application of this principle is actually not absolute, there are exceptions, such as those contained in Article 1 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Code and criminal acts categorized as extra ordinary crimes.[21] Both rules are basically applications of the principles in criminal law, therefore it is not strange that many people argue that the principle of non-retroactivity only applies to material criminal law.[22] This is further strengthened if article 28 i of the 1945 Constitution above is interpreted with existing methods of legal interpretation, it can be seen that the article is intended only for criminals, especially material crimes. In addition to the problem of limited criminal law capabilities in tackling crime, our criminal law is also less adaptive in responding to developments that occur in society, both national and international communities.[23]

The prohibition against imposing a criminal provision retroactively arises directly from the classical foundation of the principle of legality. Legal certainty, the principle that there must be guilt on the part of the accused (*schuldbeginsel*) and the purpose of the aforesaid prevention together imply that the provisions of the criminal law shall not apply retroactively.[24] However, this must be understood within the limits that retroactive force may be applied if it is done for the benefit of the accused (compare Article 1 of the Criminal Code, paragraph (2)). Where there is new legislation or a change in existing legislation that turns out to benefit the defendant, such provision can and must be applied to the defendant.[25]

The discussion of retroactive principles will stop if we only refer to the provisions in Article 1 paragraph (1) and Article 1 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Code, because these articles limit the retroactive understanding only to transitory states or become transitory law (law in transitional period).[26] This means that if previously there were no criminal regulations, then new criminal regulations were made and applied to past crimes, it means that it is not a retroactive issue, and this by Barda Nawawi Arief is included in the issue of legal sources. But if we interpret it more broadly, retroactive means retroactive and this means applicable to talk of there (meaning transitory law) or no criminal regulation before the act is committed.[12] The retroactive problem itself arises as a consequence of the application of the principle of legality. The principle of legality itself can be studied based on various aspects, such as historical aspects, socio-criminological aspects, aspects of legal development in relation to iterative and linear views, aspects related to criminal politics and studies from our *weltanschauung* perspective, namely Pancasila.[27] The study of each of these aspects has different implications regarding the principle of legality which in the view of science the difference will actually enrich the repertoire of criminal law itself.

The provisions regarding the retroactive application of this principle reappear in the Explanation to Article 4, Article 18 paragraph (3) of Law No. 39 of 1999 (specifically relating to criminal law) and Article 43 of Law No. 26 of 2000. The application of this retroactive principle raises several problems, namely: The placement and application of the retroactive principle in the Explanation to Article 4 in Law No. 39 of 1999 is contradictory to the article described,

namely Article 4. The provision in Article 4 specifies that "the right not to be prosecuted on the basis of retroactive law, including any human rights that cannot be abridged under any circumstances and by anyone." The provision not to be prosecuted on the basis of retroactive law according to Barda Nawawi Arief is an absolute right.[28] From this there are two things that arise, first, whether absolute rights can be excluded or distorted and second whether in our statutory system deviations from a provision can be made in the "explanation" section. The contradictory thing about this provision is that Article 4 stipulates absolute rights and in its explanation actually limits these absolute rights. This means that absolute rights have been undermined and do not become absolute rights anymore and become relative rights.[29]

Then about the explanation of the word "anyone", in fact only the state can apply this retroactive principle, while individuals or members of society cannot do so. In the criminal justice system, those who can run the system are law enforcement officials who perform tasks on behalf of the state, making it less likely that individuals or members of the public are involved in the system.[30] It seems that the application of the retroactive principle in Law No. 39 of 1999 and Law No. 26 of 2000 is questionable considering that the latest provisions regarding the handling of cases of gross human rights violations, namely the Rome Statute of 1998 affirm the rejection of the application of the retroactive principle. Is this a setback.[31] In general, constitutional law has the authority, namely regarding matters related to the state, meaning that anything that is bound by the state can be said to be still within the scope of constitutional law discussion. Both in the form of constitutional structures, institutions in the state or the relationship of one organ with certain organs in the state, and discusses the relationship between state structures and citizens.[32]

Aspects of Constitutional Law affect the implementation of the retroactive principle in extradition treaties between the two countries

In essence, when there is behavior from society that is governed by law, it can be said that the state is a state of law. It is known that, Indonesia is a country of law. With respect to law, basically justice is closely related to law. This is supported by the view of people who state that law can become truly meaningful as law if justice is combined with law.[33] One of the laws that is part of public law is constitutional law. Basically, the law that has the function to regulate the structure and form of government in a country along with the relationship related to power contained in equipment with each other and also the relationship between parts of the state and the state is the definition of constitutional law when interpreted in general.[34] Law and practice that has a function to regulate the collective mind of the people in a country and also noble values and has a mechanism for the relationship between state institutions and citizens and also between state institutions is also the meaning of constitutional law.[35]

Legally applicable principles and principles are discussions found in general constitutional law. Meanwhile, the discussion of constitutional law that applies at a certain time and applies to a place is a discussion contained in positive constitutional law. In essence, the law that regulates the organization of power of a state and also all aspects related to the organization of the state is the meaning of constitutional law.[17] In relation to the constitutional law, it is known that there are two functions of Indonesian constitutional law, namely as a legal basis for the establishment of the Indonesian national legal system and also as a legal basis for the formation of the organizational structure and work relations of the Republic of Indonesia.[36] In general, constitutional law has the authority, namely regarding matters related to the state, meaning that anything that is bound by the state can be said to be still within the scope of constitutional law discussion. Both in the form of constitutional structures, institutions in the state or the relationship of one organ with certain organs in the state, and discusses the relationship between state structures and citizens.[37]

The scope of authority possessed by constitutional law is very large, but in this discussion if connected with this research there are several scopes of study, as the legal authority of constitutional law to be discussed among them as follows:

- 1.The first is about the style of government of a country whether classified as a practical dictatorship, democracy, nationalist, or classified into the pattern of liberal government.
- 2.Second, it is about the outline of the acting officer regarding the judiciary, government and legislation
- 3.The third is about the relationship between the people and their state in this case is the relationship between the people and state servants, the rights and obligations of both individuals or groups as citizens and how to exercise the rights and guarantees of citizens' rights.
- 4.The fourth is about how the people exercise their constitutional rights both regarding elections, referendums, how to express opinions both oral and written and about the party system.[38]

Overall, the authority of constitutional law in the formation of law in Indonesia certainly has a special relationship or can be said to be special. This is also related to the existence of positive constitutional law itself, where positive constitutional law is constitutional law that applies in a country then has a certain position in this case related to state needs.[37] With definite provisions regarding the reach of constitutional law itself, it is clear and certain, in the formation of law in Indonesia itself constitutional law has a very important role or position, which cannot be abandoned. Based on the details above, it has simply explained the role of constitutional law itself in discussing the laws that apply in Indonesia today.[39] Simply put, constitutional law itself plays a role in all lines of law in Indonesia, especially those related to the state, both state institutions and state government directly, in order to help

review and form legal policies in accordance with the Basic Law, namely the 1945 Constitution while creating laws that play an active role in the running of the state and laws that have certainty in the implementation process so that they are not only beneficial Some parties only and avoid losing benefits to ordinary people who do not understand the law.[40]

Philipus M. Hadjon, in one of his writings, quoted D. H. Meuwissen said that constitutional law (classical) usually concerns two pillars of constitutional law, namely state organizations and citizens. In the organization of the state is regulated the form of the state and the system of government including the division of state power or state equipment.[41] While Jimly Asshiddiqie in his book "Fundamentals of Post-Reformation Indonesian Constitutional Law" mentions the basic material of Constitutional Law (positive) includes compulsory material and elective material. The compulsory material consists of the 1945 Constitution, constitutional organization and structure, citizens and human rights, theory and practice of constitutional justice, and theory and practice of state administrative justice.[35] Legal products or legislation as objects of constitutional law contain elements of dynamics that are closely related to the movements and needs of individuals in society and the growth of state organizations. Given the interrelation between constitutional law and social changes, it is evident that what is important in constitutional law is not just to study the Constitution and laws and regulations, but more emphasis should be given to the process of law. To determine the appropriate legal substance, this formation process must pay attention to the development and needs of the community with all its aspects, and then the technical design problem becomes the task of the "legislative drafter". Although a constitution is a legal document, the process of its formation is closely related to the political field, so that the role of different times, different images in determining its substance is great.[42]

The interrelationship between law and societal reality requires an analysis of the role of law in driving social changes. Indirect influence will be felt on certain social institutions, such as education, family, politics, economics, administration, and so on. Here the renewal of the system will encourage changes in society. Direct influence can be in the form of shifting and changing the values prevailing in society that hinder development by forming new laws as a means of control. It is thus clear that law is a reflection and on the contrary also influences the direction of social change, because law is not only a symptom of society, but an element of society. Where there is law, there is society [ubi ius, ibi societas].[42] In this context, awareness and renewal of the way of thinking in the field of constitutional law are needed, so that legal narrowness caused by the lack of breadth of legal treasury no longer appears in the form of legal thinking or *juridisch* solely, which results in a short-sighted way of thinking in the form of imitating the sound of regulations only. Constitutional Law not only pays attention to the formal point of view, but also the functional point of view, so it will always be dynamic.

III. Conclusion

The application of this retroactive principle is actually not absolute, there are exceptions, such as those contained in Article 1 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Code and crimes categorized as *extra ordinary crimes*. Both rules are basically applications of the principles in criminal law, therefore it is not strange that many people argue that the *principle of non-retroactivity* only applies to material criminal law. In the context of extradition, the application of the retroactive principle may involve several considerations that need attention. The application of this principle is actually not absolute, there are exceptions, such as those contained in Article 1 paragraph (2) of the Criminal Code and criminal acts categorized as *extra ordinary crimes*. Both rules are basically applications of the principles in criminal law, therefore it is not strange that many people argue that the principle of non-retroactivity only applies to material criminal law. The retroactive problem itself arises as a consequence of the application of the principle of legality. The principle of legality itself can be studied based on various aspects, such as historical aspects, socio-criminological aspects, aspects of legal development in relation to iterative and linear views, aspects related to criminal politics and studies from our *weltanschauung* perspective, namely Pancasila.

Basically, the law that has the function to regulate the structure and form of government in a country along with the relationship related to power contained in equipment with each other and also the relationship between parts of the state and the state is the definition of constitutional law when interpreted in general. Law and practice that has the function of regulating the collective mind of the people in a country and also noble values and has a mechanism for the relationship of state institutions with citizens. With definite provisions regarding the reach of constitutional law itself, it is clear and certain, in the formation of law in Indonesia itself constitutional law has a very important role or position, which cannot be abandoned. Based on the details above, it has simply explained the role of constitutional law itself in discussing the laws that apply in Indonesia today. Legal products or legislation as objects of constitutional law contain elements of dynamics that are closely related to the movements and needs of individuals in society and the growth of state organizations. Given the interrelation between constitutional law and social changes, it is evident that what is important in constitutional law is not just to study the Constitution and laws and regulations, but more emphasis should be given to the process of law

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